

On Quantum Tangential Spacetime as a finite Hilbert-space

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Abstract:

Nature knows no zero. On a fundamental level there is a minimal length. If there has to be a sort of quantum-spacetime it can not include fourvectors but must be described in tensor-form from first principles. Every coordinate, even in tangential spacetime without gravity-force has constant components in other dimensional directions, which can't be set to zero but must be defined over Planck-lengths. In this case tangential spacetime has to be rewritten in a corrected form. This rewriting will be done. Maybe, from this calculation there can later derived a consistent version of quantum gravity, which leads to finite physical states in this theory. In $T_Q(M)$, there is ergo constructed a Frobenius-scalarproduct of matrices and therefore a finite Hilbert-space. A Hilbert space is a real or complex vector space H with a dot product $\langle ., . \rangle$, which is complete with respect to the norm induced by the dot product, i.e. in which every Cauchy sequence converges. A Hilbert space is therefore a complete pre-Hilbert space. Therefore the matrix space $K(m \times n)$ of the real or complex matrices with the Frobenius -scalar product is a Hilbertspace.

Key-words:

Quantum-lineelement; quantum tangential spacetime; finite Hilbert-space; Planck-length; metron; fundamental Ricci-scalar; Planck-Minkowski-lattice.

1. Introduction:

Citation: M.v.Laue: "Strictly speaking, the world lines of two bodies cannot intersect, but can only pass close to each other." (*"Die Weltlinien zweier Körper können sich genaugenommen nicht schneiden, sondern nur nahe aneinander vorübergehen."*).[1.]

Planck-length is defined as the smallest physical length-size and from this principle must be derived a consistent description of spacetime.[2.] The first trying is to formulate this principle in tangential spacetime to see what consequences there are and if this description can be done in a

consistent form without contradictions or if it has to be denied. From this first principles every spacetime-coordinate is coupled over constant coefficients to each other coordinate in sizes of Planck-length. This change of paradigm means, that there are no fourvectors any longer but every coordinate must be described over a line-vector, so that the whole fourvectors mutate into a tensorlike matrix even in tangential spacetime. (Example given: There is no sphere in real fourdimensional spacetime $O(3,1)$ but only a minimal polyeder in subspace $O(3)$ with a finite, maximal number of edges, points and corners which can evolve in $O(3,1)$. „Real“spheres belong to affine Hausdorff-pointspaces in mathematics, where the minimal distance between two events can be set to zero. See also the comment of Richard Feynman on the theorem of Banach-Tarski). There must be a group or even a mathematical form, where as well as the summing but also the difference leads to a minimal neutral element of addition of the spacetime greater than zero. In full consequence from this idea there are no points in spacetime (and also no point-particles or pointlike events), which means also there are no point-coordinates. Every pointlike coordinate has to be developed into a linevector and so every fourvector must be a matrix of a fourtensor with some constant coefficients even in tangential spacetime, which can be possibly later developed to consistent quantum gravity descriptions. Even, if symmetric tensors are assumed, where the 64 components can reduced to 36 components, there mustn't be zeros in the known 28 other components but minimally constant numbers which lead to constant fundamental length of r_{PL} . In general fact this leads to an eightdimensional theory, which can in this special case but folded to a well known fourdimensional description. The usual restriction to rectangular coordinates in SRT-described tangential spacetime is used. [3.]

2.Methods/Calculations:

The coordinate- transition, which has to be made, is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &\rightarrow (x/r_{PL}/r_{PL}/r_{PL}) \\
 y &\rightarrow (r_{PL}/y/r_{PL}/r_{PL}) \\
 z &\rightarrow (r_{PL}/r_{PL}/z/r_{PL}) \\
 ct &\rightarrow (r_{PL}/r_{PL}/r_{PL}/ct).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1a-d.)}$$

This is a transition, where every spacetime coordinate has a constant Planck-Length component in the other three dimension-directions. In this case, every pointlike coordinate becomes a line-vector. If there is only the contemplation of two parallel moving inertial systems with constant velocity v in x, ct -direction, than the components of y, z has also to be reduced to Planck-length r_{PL} . Ergo, every coordinate point-component must be translated into a line-vector, so the whole fourvector for a spacetime-event becomes a tensorlike four-matrix even in $T_Q(M)$, not only in case of gravity. Then there is a transition of the classical form of lineelement-product too:

$$s^2 = \eta_{i,k} \cdot x^i \cdot x^k \rightarrow s^2 = \hat{\eta}_{i,k} \cdot A^{i,k} : A^{i,k}
 \tag{2.)}$$

where $A^{i,k} : A^{i,k}$ means the classical Frobenius scalarproduct of two real matrices. With this product there is defined a norm and the matrices build a finite Hilbert-space with all needed conditions for this space. The definition of the assigned matrices are with [4.]:

with

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\eta}_{1,1} &= n \cdot K \\
\hat{\eta}_{i,k} &= m; i \neq k \\
\hat{\eta}_{i,k} &= n; i, k = 2; 3; \\
\hat{\eta}_{4,4} &= n \cdot (1 - K).
\end{aligned}
\quad m, n \in \mathbb{N} \tag{3a-d.}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
A^{1,1} &= x; \\
A^{i,k} &= r_{PL}, i \neq k \neq 1; 4. \\
A^{4,4} &= c \cdot t
\end{aligned}
\tag{4a-c.}$$

for a movement of two inertial systems I_1 and I_2 parallel to x-axis with $v = \text{const.}$.

With Frobenius scalar product of two matrices, [4.],[5.] this leads to the correct quantized lineelement of tangential spacetime $T_Q(M)$ in following form. This lineelement includes 64 elements instead of 4 by classical Minkowski-tangential spacetime without quantization. Even if tensors are assumed as symmetric, they mustn't account any zeros but normed Planck-sizes as minimal values.

This conditions lead to the whole, complete and correct quantum-line-element of $T_Q(M)$ - tangential-spacetime metric of:

$$\begin{aligned}
s^2 &= n \cdot K \cdot x^2 + 50 \cdot m \cdot r_{PL}^2 + 3 \cdot n \cdot K \cdot r_{PL}^2 + 3 \cdot m \cdot c \cdot t \cdot r_{PL} + 3 \cdot m \cdot x \cdot r_{PL} \\
&\quad + 3 \cdot n \cdot (1 - K) \cdot r_{PL}^2 + n \cdot c^2 \cdot t^2 \cdot (1 - K).
\end{aligned}
\tag{5a.}$$

This lineelement shall be called Minkowski-quantum-spacetime (MQST) or Minkowski-Planck-lattice (MPL).

For the bounding conditions of $m=0; n=1; K \rightarrow 1; 1-K \rightarrow -1$ this quantum-lineelement gives back the classical Minkowski-lineelement in two dimensions with constant velocity of the two inertial systems parallel to x-axis with constant velocity v of:

$$s^2 = x^2 - c^2 \cdot t^2 \tag{5b.}$$

with its well known $\eta_{i,k}$ of metric tensor for no curvature.

So the correct transition and connection from the here described elementary quantum case to classical theory of unquantized SRT to this quantized system is given.

For this elementary system of parallel IS the description of coordinate-transformations can be made in four dimensions. If this folded description also can be made for whole movement in all dimensions $x, y, z, c \cdot t$ or in gravity-description is yet not known.

The local fundamental Lorentz-Planck-transformations for the quantum-lattice in two dimensions come in following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
x' &= C \cdot (x + B \cdot c \cdot t) + 2 \cdot n \cdot r_{PL} \\
y' &= n \cdot x + 3 \cdot n \cdot r_{PL} \\
z' &= n \cdot x + 3 \cdot n \cdot r_{PL} \\
ct' &= C \cdot (B \cdot x + ct) + 2 \cdot n \cdot r_{PL}
\end{aligned} \tag{6a-d.)}$$

with following abbreviations:

$$A := \frac{D \cdot E \cdot c^2 \cdot t^2}{\tau}$$

$$B := \sqrt{1 - A \cdot \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

$$C := \frac{A^2}{D} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{F}{E \cdot c^2 \cdot t^2} \right)$$

$$D := n \cdot K$$

$$E := n \cdot (1 - K)$$

$$F := 50 \cdot m \cdot r_{PL}^2 + 3 \cdot n \cdot K r_{PL}^2 + 3 \cdot m \cdot r_{PL} \cdot c \cdot t + 3 \cdot m \cdot r_{PL} \cdot x + 3 \cdot n \cdot (1 - K) \cdot r_{PL}^2$$

$$K := \frac{\hbar^2}{c^2 \cdot m^2_0} \cdot (\alpha \cdot R + \beta \cdot \Lambda); \alpha, \beta \in R. \text{ Mostly choice for both: } 1$$

$$\tau := \frac{1}{r_{PL}^2} := R_{Fund} \tag{7a-f.)}$$

τ is called a metron (after Diplom-Physicist Burkhard Heim). This is the smallest length-square of nature and can be identified with fundamental Ricci-scalar.

3.Conclusion:

A quantum Minkowski-tangential spacetime can be constructed on a Planck-lattice, which for now can assumed to be static, not dynamic. Gravity is not included yet but it can be seen, that the quantized metric lineelement must have 64 components instead of four, like in classical Minkowski-spacetime. Even, if some of them are set to constant coefficients, there can't be a zero but it must be build a minimal, positive size. Possibly, an advanced quantum gravity theory can be build with a lineelement of 64 components. This doesn't include the other three known physical interactions like $U(1) \times SU(2) \times SU(3)$ like in superstring- or M- theory. If this ansatz here is constructive and consistent for a quantum gravity theory, must be seen, because the mathematical descriptions for such a theory must be examined to see, if it is possible to quantize their formations of concepts.[6.]

4.Summary:

There is no choice to touch anything, no possibility. Always there is a Planck-distance between two microobjects or four-events. This distance must be seen as a minimal size of a distance. In full consequence there are no point-events in light-cone of SRT at the center but only minimal volumes.

Real spacetime is no affine Hausdorff-space with a defined zero-distance but a lattice of Planck-planes or volumes, possibly dynamic.[7.] Described is a consequent form of tangential spacetime lineelement $T_Q(M)$ in this model, which leads basically to 64 components of spacetime. Some of them can safely assumed as small and constant but not set to zero. This model has to be advanced to a gravity description.

5.Discussion:

The question is, if this model can be developed to a full gravity representation without any contradictions or if the used paradigm has to be rejected because the way of its explanation as an extension of classical SRT towards a form of QSRT will not lead to any consistent description of a quantum gravity-theory of GRT. If the underlying tensor is assumed as symmetric, the number of terms reduced from 64 to 36 components but the rest of 28 terms are not zero but different and must set to be constant. These facts must be taken into account in the further description.

6.References:

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7.Verification:

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